

JOURNEY TO SELF-CONSCIOUSNESS WITH HOLISTIC HEALING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

If a person is constantly in the past and constantly talking to you about the rules, if he is prescriptive, he can't get out of his memory, he can't get out of the data store. In other words, the person has become a mind-body person living in the collective memory card, in the world of records. There are so many analytical left-brained people around us that you recognize them by their plain logical phrases. Even if you wanted to, you cannot change their minds, move their belongings, they will not abandon their routine, they will not want to use a single pen or a glass in a different way. That glass will always be there, that pen will always be there. Stuck in the left brain, he wrote and drew himself and cannot get out of his prison. Most of the time, we see this in our mothers, fathers or parents, or in our spouse and friend. We call it what state, this state is an obsessive state related to obsessive personality structure. In psychology, obsessive people, composite people are trapped in their mind and psychological selves. They are the people in the addicted personality group. Traditional, disciplined people brought up in a patriarchal culture can't get out of their protective attitudes, so they have always remained detail-oriented and prescriptive. .

Keywords: ' Holistic Healing, ' Holistic Healing Techniques, Self- Awareness , Psychology

1. So, in which herd did you stay, and from what level of consciousness is your consciousness reading life?

Maybe you're playing an extra in someone else's story. Victim self, bitter self, judge Do you know your self, your child self? From whom could you have copied your subconscious? Think about it... These things happen a lot in society. Sometimes we see a victim self that never lived, who inherited the fate of its parent who died forty years ago.

Sometimes, we come across cases that say, I look like my uncle, cough like him, I can't breathe like my uncle, and say that I will get cancer like him, and that really makes him cancer.

Or ; life is very hard and my mother has survived by working her whole life. Sometimes ; Man has been imprisoned in his pain body and emotional right brain, saying that he can survive by always sacrificing and serving constantly .

inherited the emotional karma in the ancestral records , lives a life of captivity affixed to a painful consciousness , and does not even know about himself. Unfortunately, most of us live this way and die as unconscious and automatic pain-bodies.

2. How Do We Get Out of These Mixed Life Cycles?

reason and journey to our essence, we will get to know our body, our faculties, that is, our attributes and abilities very well. As the owners of clean minds; We will always strive to be people who research, read , reason , have knowledge, have a developed anterior frontal cortex, and are adult conscious people.

How should our intentions be in a positive way?

In this limitless dimension of consciousness, I open all my perceptions, my entire system of consciousness, all of my celestial attributes to serve the wholeness by combining them with divine intelligence in a way that will manifest from me.

I am now and now at one with infinite consciousness and unlimited resources, removing my negative programs and separatist ego illusion from my life program.

3. Attention and Focus

The power of our intentions and our awareness of mind are very important for our life, the reason is that our thoughts are stray and scattered, reducing their frequency at any moment with their saboteur nature. If the mind reminds you of something from the past, for example, a picture brought back your mother, your father, the discussion in the morning, etc. you should know that your left brain is going way ahead and you are regressed stuck in the past . You're stuck with your childhood, you're stuck with last night. You are unconsciously living in the past, stuck in

the past, you have many windows open there and your mind is living under the influence of the psychological world.

In this body grip, if I am stuck with my parents who come with an image, if I am stuck with past memories that come with an image, I can be an energy vampire feeding on the energy of others right now. If I think about the life of others from where I am sitting now, I have probably entered the energy field of my mother or father and I am encroaching on the free living space. My energy continues to serve a corrupt system full of unconsciously karma-creating addictions. That's why you need to discover the mind map that acts out of control, you need to discover mind patterns, emotion patterns, life patterns. What do you call life? what do you call life? What's in your perceptual system? What are the movies that revolve in your mind in the content of the concepts, what are the stories that revolve in your brain? You need to see these.

- Where is my dividing part? What is my past piece?
- You should look at which ones you have and which ones you don't.
- You should draw examples from your past thoughts and states, from your own states.
- Did I get out of the mental prison today?
- mental prison sometimes gives you a house, you can't leave your house.
- mental prison sometimes gives you a job, you can't leave the workplace.

That mental prison sometimes gives you feelings, you can never get out of those feelings. Sometimes it gives you the consciousness of absence, throws your mind into the void and makes you stupid by lowering your energy under the guise of nothingness. You are incapable of even being yourself and it is impossible to realize the manifestation of your self- existence here. You need to know that in your absence, nothingness is also a mind fiction and that it distracts you at that point. In order to solve these mind blockages, we first need to breathe properly and question our thoughts. Yes now where will my left brain take me or where will my right brain take me? Right-brained people also generate a lot of anxiety and anxiety because they look at life from the center of the future. Left-brained people, I said stubborn, I said analytical, they try to connect everything to this world. They try to put it in order, everything will be in order, it will be on time. They cannot exist without including themselves in a program. It's the house that made it. His house will be clean, everything will be in order. The only thing that creates him is order, matter, or the only thing that creates him is the success of his child, his wife's interest and concern for him.

It is still not in its essence, and it is still not in itself. He still lives in the illusion world he has created and finds himself

in a news situation to know. How can we awaken this person's consciousness now?

4. Which Brain Lobe Do You Live With?

The creative right brain is an area that is blunted and suppressed by the rote education model imposed at an early age. If the child is not freed at the age of 0.7, if he has not grown up in love and trust, if he is not given the chance to think freely, unfortunately his self-esteem will be weak. If he has been subjected to severe emotional pressure by his parents, he will experience insecurity and take on an introverted emotional personality.

grew up with unbalanced people, whose mother and father traumas are high, whose perception systems are deteriorated and their right analytical creative brains shrink. Science proves to us that the unused brain lobe loses its function over time and changes in size. In other words, while the used part of the brain is active and developing, our unused lobe continues to get smaller and smaller. Thus, a brain as small as a walnut, unused, with millions of neurons that have not fired, becomes fertilizer for the soil.

in an environment of peace, in an environment of trust and accustomed to free thinking were measured and it was determined that their brain lobes were developed. When the brain of a child who has experienced traumatic events, disconnected from nature, is compared with the restless family environment, an incredible difference has emerged. This means that our biological structure is directly affected by the environment, education and all living conditions in our world.

- What did we experience in our childhood, what did we encounter, how were our environmental factors?
- We constantly carry traces of these in our personality structure, and it is very important to be aware of them.

What happens is that self-consciousness is completely suppressed and withdrawn by our monster ego. As a child, the mind takes over the entire life due to fears and pressures. Since the child is a copy of its parent, it continues to carry on the automatic behaviors that have been

approved in the past. All humanity continues as a copy of each other with the copy-paste system. And man lives as an unopened self- consciousness , an unread book.

In accordance with the law of unity and unity in the universe, you are the one who speaks, you are the one who listens, and you are the one who develops your understandings with your experiences. You are the only one in an observed and observed universe and you actually live only in your own frequency dimension with your created consciousness.

both everything in wave and frequency dimensions and nothing in quantum dimension . We are connected to a single soul energy, a universal infinite energy that creates all existence, its mouth, its tongue, its eyes, its ear, its hand, its foot, its breath.

Our search for meaning begins when things get confused, cramped and overwhelmed, when the earth and sky change places, when we feel too lost to see the direction we need to go. Our self-consciousness can only show us our direction and ourselves . Whenever you follow your heart's route, you will feel happy and all your choices will always be right.

Just as a water buffalo senses the water source behind a hill that it cannot see without knowing why, so we instinctively move towards the areas where our souls feel closest without knowing it.

Feeling love with our heart is our biggest addiction! Often we create our pain, over and over again, alcohol, cigarettes, neurotic obsessions, illnesses, depression, stomach shrinkage, failures, disregards, self-pity, fears in the name of compassion. Without acknowledging our blind ignorance, we unconsciously blame ourselves for everything we do , go back and forth on this karma. We'll meet inside.

Unfortunately, while our direction appears to be happiness, salvation, awakening, it is actually towards unhappiness, bondage and darkness.

Trying to get rid of our pain and ignorance is for most of us the same as abandoning our essence. means; it means to be directionless, to be lost. Therefore, towards happiness

All our attempts are doomed to failure as if it were our destiny. Moreover, everything and anyone who tries to save us from this situation will turn into an enemy for us, as it will leave us directionless and take away our definition of identity.

ironic that our enemies are also our saviors !

5. Enlightened Human Model

First of all , the new human model; He is a person who reveals and lives his own knowledge, not someone else's knowledge. In other words, there will be a being who can use the results of the knowledge that he has realized, cooked and handled in his own soul, conscience and consciousness, and the self-knowledge that occurs in his soul .

In this information, there is information about the physical universe, as well as information about the spiritual universe and its own spirit. This is the real basis. We strongly anticipate that the human being of the future will be an entity that can withstand both the spiritual universe and the physical universe and establish common areas with it.

- If we really want to get rid of our ignorance, we must raise our awareness, give ourselves a new
- We have to find a roadmap, develop a new addiction. This addiction is towards the light, towards the courage,
- neurotic obsessions.
- Even in deep sleep, our dreams can be realized, as our inner self will pull us in one direction under all circumstances.
- It should be strong enough to determine its direction. He has to leave a very enjoyable job unfinished because he needs to sleep.
- Just as the first thing that comes to mind when a person with a mental illness opens his eyes in the morning is his job in the evening, our essence is without thinking, without being taught, when we open our eyes to the next life and take our first breath.
- be what we are inclined to do . Our love for ourselves must take over our consciousness to the point where it transcends even death. Then it will be inevitable to reach enlightenment and end ignorance.
- What is your self-definition?
- When it comes to the issue of self-awareness, awareness starts from you and your self-knowledge.
- It is about learning your own nature. First of all, how does our biological machine
- measure and define its working and capacity . Because in order to develop it, we need to know it and discover its features and limits. How can I cross those limits?

- frontal cortex of the brain , that is, the frontal lobe, is always open to research, learning and development.
- And the current human consciousness and brain are in the midst of amazing discoveries and discoveries. His energy and aura are so high that he is able to work energetically in an astral way, without using his body yet . Seeing people reading the universe, seeing people doing telepathy is not a miracle at all, it's not a secret at all.
- communicate telepathically, treat diseases with their bioenergy , and make new discoveries through astral travels.

6. How Does Awareness Occur?

- If I'm addicted to the past and thinking of others from where I'm sitting now, my mother or my father
- I have probably entered the energy field of others and continue to create mixed events.
- In order to conserve your energy in such a chaotic and corrupt system, you must first discover your own mind map.
- need to discover your emotional structure, thought patterns, egoic tendencies . You must first face yourself by gaining the awareness of asking questions.
- What do you call life? How would you describe yourself? What is your intelligence level, perception style?
- Beyond concepts and memorization, what are the voices in your brain saying and which movies are playing in your mind?
- You need to realize these and know yourself. I will give you some tips to get to know your ego and self. Our ego represents our separatist and divisive side , let's call it the tyrant in short , our core self is our main source from infinity and the real wisdom belongs to it.
- The tyrant ego divides and separates; the wise soul does not discriminate. The tyrant presupposes the ego; The wise soul sees and knows.
- The overbearing ego tries to live in the past and future and exist in the present; wise soul in the present
- ceases to exist. The tyrant ego blocks; supports the wise soul. The tyrant ego believes in desires; wise soul to a purified heart. The tyrant ego divides and separates; the wise soul does not discriminate.

- The tyrant ego kills; wise spirit lives.
- The overbearing ego brings awareness into the mind; The wise soul brings the mind into awareness.
- The overbearing ego is governed by thoughts; The wise soul governs your thoughts.
- The overbearing ego tries to control; the wise soul surrenders. The tyrant keeps the ego; wise soul leaves.
- The tyrant has the ego; wise soul, it happens. For the tyrant there is a dancer and he is the only truth; For the wise there is dance and it is the only truth.
- The bully is afraid; wise is brave. The tyrant hurts; The wise understand and have compassion.
- The tyrant writhes in pain; the sage stands still.
- The tyrant sees what he is instructed to see; The wise see what is.
- The tyrant knows what he is told to know; the wise know what is.
- “What will I achieve?” in order for the bully to take action. he asks; wise, lost in movement,
- freed from questions and expectations. The tyrant knows himself; The wise forget themselves.
- The tyrant thinks he is me; The wise know that there is no such thing as me .
- The tyrant is mortal; sage is immortal.

7. What is Quantum Thinking?

Quantum Thinking is a high quality way of thinking. Ordinary thought forms are repetitive, ineffective, and limited energies. They do not have the power to change or create. Rather, it flows in the form of delusions, delusions, and stray dreams. However, Quantum Thinking is a form of creative thinking that can be effective at a very deep level, in the subatomic field.

- It includes specially constructed verbal and imaginary formations by entering a special level of consciousness.
- At this level, man becomes the master of his own life.
- Quantum Thinking further operates in the field of collective intelligence. When you cooperate with the energy that evolves the whole universe, you transcend the limited possibilities of being a "person" and reach the power of the "whole".

- In time, your strength will of course be equal to the strength of the whole.
- What is the connection between quantum physics and quantum thinking technique?
- Quantum physics puts us in a field where physical matter in the classical sense is transformed into energy. In that field, subatomic particles are now nothing but rapidly moving energy particles.
- Moreover, these particles respond to the energy emitted by human thought. It turns out that the person observing this field and the piece he observes are not independent, disconnected things. The distinctions between thought and energy, between the observer and the observed, between the inside and the outside, between here and beyond, are lifted.

The thought packets we send add to this area, which Heisenberg calls the uncertainty area. It makes it obvious. Our impact on one point of the quantum field also affects the whole. When you think of something, the whole field is affected. Quantum physics is the name of a point where physics and metaphysics intermingle.

, scientists have been investigating how the consciousness created in living things came into existence . Previously, it was accepted that human consciousness existed from the stage when it began to form in the mother's womb.

However, with the quantum theory, this belief left its place to another theory. According to quantum theory, consciousness was actually a kind of energy, and while scientists were trying to unravel the secret of this energy, they encountered another fact.

According to this theory, it is the reality and the constant existence of the energy existing in the universe of Einstein . Dr. With this basis, David Hamilton said that human consciousness is constantly present in the universe through quantum particles and is transferred to the human being when he is born into the physical world. Think of it like an automation programmed with the help of a computer. You produce a device, you give commands to automation with the help of codes, so that when the final level is reached, it will be loaded . When the device you produce reaches the final level, automation makes the loading you ordered to the device.

Dr. According to David Hamilton, consciousness actually always existed, it was transferred to the physical human body as a result of the order given when a person was born. Dr. "I believe each of us existed before we were born on earth," Hamilton said in a statement.

Dr. According to Hamilton, when a person is born, consciousness is uploaded to the physical device called the body, and when the physical device named body expires, that is, when you die, consciousness is transferred to another realm.

8. Mind Programming

Your mind programs consist of automatic and memory-based areas you know or do not know that you have learned and recorded throughout your life. All positive and negative records should be reviewed and determined. You should look at the past consciousnesses you received from your ancestors, which ones you have and which ones you don't. You should learn lessons by contemplating your past thoughts and situations, and the events that have happened to you. Breathing and meditation should be the most important part of our lives, the best way out of the mental prison. When your minds are thinking positively, it is so peaceful and delicious that it is like a nice spring breeze, like a magnificent pasture . It is a corner of paradise that your dreams can reach , you are like lying on the green grass or like a soft stream flowing from the hills. Your piece of mind was like a blank page when you remembered your childhood, because you didn't know anything yet. You were completely naive and had no prejudices. You are just curious, enthusiastic. Knowing the holism in the universe, your child's heart is watching the completely curtainless world . You are living freely and alive . There is excitement in your heart. Because you have the beginning mind. See, when people with child consciousness and old, conscious and experienced people come together, a great energy will be released. This freshness of the child mind will make them feel very good, but their old mind will not do you very well.

Unfortunately, people have prejudices and fixed perspectives due to their negative experiences and begin to radiate negative energy into the collective space.

However, human beings are a miracle, they are divine, and they create all universes thanks to their creative power. Namely;

- * It has 20 Trillion Cells.

- * Carries 96,000 km of Blood Vessels.

- * It has a Heart that pumps 9000 liters of blood by beating 100,000 times a day.

- * A Brain that receives/sends 100,000 messages per minute,
- * 75 km long Nerves,
- * Lungs that take 11,000 liters of air every day,
- * Two Kidneys that clean the blood of the whole body every 5 minutes,
- * 7 mt Small Intestine, 2 mt Large Intestine,
- * 230 bones,
- * A Nose that can recognize 50,000 different scents,
- * A Language that can taste 10,000 different Flavors,
- * Two Ears that can hear hundreds of different frequencies

Two Eyes that can see in 576 MegaPixel quality,

- * And it is equipped with material and spiritual feelings and blessings.

Are you looking for proof of the existence of the Creator with such a perfectly functioning miraculous body?

He who knows himself knows his Lord, that is, his creator, we are always building our lives with the 'Quantum Brain'.

All electromagnetic waves based on the five senses or beyond the five senses coming to your brain are evaluated by this organ according to the database, forming your perceptual world in the form of a holographic multidimensional image! In other words, you do not live in the outside world, you live in the dream world formed inside your brain, whoever you are!

- Everything you perceive and judge is a symbol of what you perceive in your own world!
- Everyone lives in their own world and will live forever.
- The more real your world feels to you, the more real your heaven or hell will be.
- Everyone, everything in their world; Everything that makes you happy, happy or sad is caused by the values that make up the database .
- All the attributes of the Creator, namely the esma features, are present in your brain and these esma features emerge from you at every moment.

At the moment, just as our brain receives and evaluates various information coming from outside according to the current knowledge base and creates our world accordingly, since this structure is immortal, it continues to live, even after it has experienced the state of leaving the body, which is called death.

The quantum brain's information software continues after life ends, with or without a body. In the spiritual and energetic dimension, a person lives forever. Therefore, the person does not die, the flesh body dies.

your hologram world, you begin to see beings, just like when you are living right now, but these beings are beings created by evaluating in your brain and created by your Lord . Just like you saw in your dream last night, your consciousness continues to gain consciousness in different frequency sizes.

In short; The quantum brain operates according to your choices and creations. If you realize this, you can immediately start searching for your core self and your own truth. As you begin to become conscious, your mind begins to work more purely and without prejudice.

At this stage, we need our starting mind. In order to reach the Path of the Heart, you need to be able to silence, recognize and manage the mind, everything you do unconsciously remains amateur . Whether the student can safely pass through here depends on the strength of his spirit. If at this stage he remembers his initial mind, reminds himself of his task, then he can say to himself:

A person becomes who he practices, not who he wants to be. When he sets out, gains experience, he only remembers the love he seeks, the true “ I ” and the Truth . He wonders why he went on such a path. He set out because he is beaten in life, he is dirty . He started out because that woman or man is giving him the opportunity to be what he is. He started out because what he is is not his real state. The way he is, the emotions he feels, the pain he suffers are all a result of his practices. What he calls my life is nothing but the actions he constantly repeats, develops habits and addictions, and does without thinking anymore. These repeated actions have transformed him into the person he thinks he is, not the person he wants to be.

- He set out on this path to develop habits that will allow him to be the person he truly is. When he remembers this, he realizes that he needs to get a little more dirty. In this way, it is polluted voluntarily.

- It is polluted by striving harder for virtue, by doing more research, practices , meditations. Then the belt around his waist turns almost black with the dust, sweat and filth of years of training and training. It is now completely contaminated. The person has gained full experience. A black belt is worn around the waist.
- Now the real training begins. This workout is made to forget. The person has learned how to punch, kick and grapple accurately and effectively. Now he has to forget that he is training, punching or kicking. So that he can fight with perfect moves without thinking, without being hindered by his mind, without fear or enthusiasm. Likewise, the person walking on the path of the self and the heart should forget that he is doing virtuous actions, that he is aware, that he is walking on the path of Truth, and that he is doing it. So much so that virtue must be its true nature and must be revealed and practiced without restriction, without reflection, without the need for comparisons.
- Then, slowly, his dirt, his experiences begin to leave him . He knows that experience is his friend and foe. Prejudice and compulsion in experience disappear just as impure metals melt into molten gold. His heart is as pure as gold. Over the years, the black belt on her waist wears off from work and begins to turn white. So much so that, as a result of many years and efforts, the belt on his waist becomes almost white. This indicates that he has returned to his original purity.

As we walk the Path of the Heart towards our own selves, we gradually return to our child naivety that we are unaware of. We realize that virtue is our true nature. As we get dirty with right actions, we leave our habits that we initially gained through imperfect practices, and forget the person we think we are. This is how we become who we really are.

This is called "getting where we are". There is no other place to be.

9. Vibration and Frequency Law

Thought is energy. Energy constantly vibrates, creating an oscillation. As human beings, we are constantly vibrating energies. Since our vibration level is low, we continue our lives as a mass body, which is precipitated on the earth. We can see the energies vibrating in accordance with our vibration as mass in our own vibrational world (other people, animals, table, chair etc.). The natural vibration level of the human body is an average of 300 vibrations per second.

People who are too involved in worldly affairs are under this vibration. As the frequency, that is, the vibration level, increases, the supernatural powers of the people also increase. The vibration levels of people who have the power to heal are on average 500 vibrations per second. When the 800 vibration level is reached, the psychic powers emerge. Above 1000 vibrations, the telepathy channel is very fluently open. A person at the level of 10 thousand vibrations per second becomes able to astral travel.

We can see each other, but we cannot see living things vibrating at 10 thousand times a second. We call them transdimensional beings. Few of us, the people we call psychics, can contact them. Sometimes they can claim to receive information from them as a channel. Some of these people may have schizophrenia, some may be swindlers, but it is known that there are people who exceed the notion of time and place by increasing the vibration level above 10 thousand per second. Your Miracle is Your Vibration and Frequency .

Twenty years ago, the universe was actually a huge vibration. is If it were said , the human of the small universe would also vibrate at every moment with everything around him. that the secret of life is hidden in vibrations . What would you think if told ?

100 years ago, Nikola Tesla was talking about his own invention, the earthquake machine . lyrics He said : “ In a few , seconds , I felt the building begin to shake. If I had continued for ten more minutes, I could have destroyed the building and the street .

Brooklyn with same device Bridge “Less than 1 hour I could have landed it in the East River .”

Tesla had partially solved the secret of frequencies , namely vibrations . to Tesla According to him, the universe was one big vibration , and we were all in this vibration. We were a small reflection. Or in other words , the universe is a guitar, we are its strings and other We are vibrating all the time with all the strings . Scientists have been trying to make sense of this song for centuries , and they finally discovered the sheet music . Now I 'm trying to decipher the melody without breaking the guitar strings. they are working .

Each organ has its own “vibration . body vibration Apart from that , organs also vibrate among themselves at different speeds . For example , the vibration rate of the heart is not the same as that of the kidney . When the kidney malfunctions , it also means that there is a problem with its vibration . If you expose a person to vibrations that are not good for their heart , that person will suffer a heart attack . may die . Even remote assassinations in this way are theoretically possible .

True As vibration saves lives , wrong vibration also takes lives . Dozer users, people using asphalt drilling vibration devices have a heart attack and They are likely to die or suffer from various diseases in the long run. Because these devices are very because they have strong vibrations your body breaks the vibration .

Healing diseases with frequencies (vibrations) possible .

every vibration measure is calculated with a frequency value . Different vibrations have different frequencies. What kind of vibration is a vibration ? with the frequency values we measure .

Frequency technology is used in medicine today , albeit partially, but in the future , many The treatment of the disease can be done with frequencies. A suitable frequency will be found for each disease and the sick person will be treated by being placed in that frequency environment. Even the placebo effect is actually related to changing frequencies . The thing called believing is the patient's illness . It is nothing but the change in the frequency of the disease and the fact that the disease can no longer find a place for itself in that frequency. not . When you hold someone's hand , your body automatically tunes to their frequency. So be careful whose hand you're holding because if his magnetic field is stronger than yours, he may pull you into his frequency and that frequency may actually be a frequency that doesn't work for you.

Taino and Gary in the 1900s young healthy people's day to measure the average body frequencies within succeeded . A healthy human body has a frequency in the range of 62-72 MHz . Good We create different frequencies when we feel bad and different frequencies when we feel bad . So we have a variable frequency range , even if not as controlled as radio waves . As a result of the researches , it was determined that negative thoughts lower the human frequency by 12 MHz , while positive thoughts increase it by 10 MHz . Nikola Tesla , when we can isolate the frequencies in the human body from external frequencies , we can protect against diseases . He argued that we will show great resistance , . Yet While Tesla was alive, in 1920, Dr. Raymond Rife found that he could destroy viruses and bacteria using certain frequencies . Today , patients can be treated using frequencies.

10. Well, what are the frequencies in music that are a part of our life and the result?

People have been making music since ancient times . simple instruments powerful and complex to instruments has turned into nature and music What is the natural frequency?

Musicians and music lovers 432 hz is they say . So why 432hz? studies of ancient musicians He says they set their music to 432hz .

Standards in 1953. According to Organization (ISO) 440 frequency decides to set the music .

to many conspiracy theorists , the 440 hz frequency is nazi . how to make people restless and depressed during It's the result of their research . As a result , many people find music made with a frequency of 432 Hz more peaceful and say that they feel this frequency in their hearts .

Increase your frequency with love, awareness, breathing, meditation, music therapy..!

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